

Abstract

This paper focuses on the role of fertilizers within regional nutrient cycles. Bio-based fertilizers can contribute to regional nutrient circularity, but the question remains whether production and consumption of bio-based fertilizers is beneficial to the farmer and the environment. Therefore, both farmers' private costs and environmental externalities should be taken into account. We formulate a farm-level multi-objective optimization model by considering a range of fertilizers, their costs and the environmental consequences associated with their production and use. The cost-minimization approach is applied to a conceptualized Flemish leek farmer aiming to safeguard nutrient uptake while being constrained by nutrient standards and the availability of on-farm residues. Our results suggest that mineral fertilizers have an important role in the fertilizer mix despite their environmental externalities. Nevertheless, there is also a role for bio-based fertilizers. These results have implications for farmers and policymakers wishing to internalize fertilizer externalities.

Keywords: social cost minimization, nutrient recovery, fertilizer externalities, farm optimization, environmental impact assessment

1. Introduction

Recent years have seen a rising interest in ‘nutrient recycling’, ‘closing the nutrient loop’ and ‘circular nutrient economy’ (Harder et al., 2021; Koppelmäki et al., 2021; van der Wiel et al., 2020). The concept of nutrient circularity comprises the reduction of nutrient losses along the agri-food supply chain as well as the recovery of nutrients from organic residues for reuse in agricultural production (Harder et al., 2021). The natural balance of regional nutrient cycles has been disrupted due to the addition of external inputs and the movement of nutrients across regions through trade of bio-commodities such as fertilizers and animal feed (Harder et al., 2021). This linearization generates a two-sided problem: it raises issues of nutrient security (Cordell & White, 2015) and it compromises water, soil and air quality due to nutrient pollution (Richardson et al., 2023; Steffen et al., 2015).

This paper focuses on the role of fertilizers within regional nutrient cycles. Many technologies exist to convert organic residues into bio-based fertilizers (BBF), defined as fertilizers for which nutrients are recovered from organic residues or waste (Chojnacka et al., 2019). Established technologies are, for example, composting and anaerobic digestion (AD) of organic waste (Vaneckhaute et al., 2013). However, in order for these BBF to be applied at a large scale, they must not only ensure safety and avoid environmental and human health risks, but they also need to offer a considerate benefit to the farmer applying the fertilizer. While social networks and expert acceptance are crucial in shaping their intentions, farmers make rational decisions about fertilizers based on their costs and benefits (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024). Therefore, it is important to the farmer that these BBF increase their yield while being economically feasible. There is a lack of research focusing on identifying economically optimal fertilizer mix compositions, i.e., application rates or proportions of different fertilizers with only a few studies in this area (Bueno-Delgado et al., 2016; De Keyser et al., 2023; Macharia et al., 2016).

In addition to private costs to farmers, fertilizers bring along external costs related to their environmental emissions during production and application. In terms of external environmental impacts, previous Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) research points out that the impact of mineral fertilizers is relatively low, but that the application of locally available byproducts as organic fertilizer instead of imported mineral fertilizers provides the potential for reduced environmental impacts (Santolin et al., 2024). While environmental impact assessment methods such as LCA provide a comprehensive evaluation for the impacts associated with a

product, they rarely account for the broader societal costs that they impose. By incorporating external costs, and thereby weighting the impacts according to their damage costs, the impacts can be translated into tangible costs borne by society. External costs, while impacting society through their influence on the environment and human health, are not translated into market transactions. Therefore, it is relevant to investigate socially optimal fertilizer use, not only reflecting the private costs to the farmer but also the external costs to society. In this paper, the external costs will be centered on environmental impacts. Henceforth, the combined total of private and external costs will be referred to as social costs. While some examples of economic and environmental optimization studies exist within the BBF domain (Willeghems et al., 2016), and some efforts have been made to incorporate social costs in bio-economic optimization research (Mavrotas et al., 2015; Tiammee & Likasiri, 2020), the monetary externality valuation is missing in current optimization research in the BBF domain.

This paper aims to determine the socially optimal fertilizer mix on farm level, expressed as the application rates of different fertilizers, considering a wide range of fertilizers while incorporating private and external costs associated with the production and use of fertilizers in a cost optimization approach. Studying farm-level fertilizer mixes provides a more comprehensive understanding by reflecting agricultural practices more accurately than analyzing individual fertilizers in isolation. As a data-driven decision-making approach, the cost minimization allows for comprehensive cost accounting of both private and external costs, while ensuring economic efficiency in terms of resource optimization and simultaneously accounting for nutrient requirements and regulatory limits.

Table 1: Innovation of this study

	Existing research		Relevant studies	Innovation in this study
Economic viability of BBF	Studies identifying economically optimal fertilizer mix compositions are scarce, and do not take environmental costs into account		Bueno-Delgado et al., 2016; De Keyser et al., 2023; Macharia et al., 2016	Investigating economically optimal fertilizer mix considering private and external costs
Environmental viability of BBF	LCA studies rarely translate the environmental impacts in monetary terms to compare them to private costs, and rarely reflect an optimization of different possibilities within a realistic agricultural system		Mavrotas et al., 2015; Santolin et al., 2024; Tiammee & Likasiri, 2020; Willeghems et al., 2016	Incorporating environmental impacts into the evaluation by translating them into tangible costs borne by society, in addition to private costs

This approach is applied to a conceptualized horticultural farmer in Flanders, Belgium. More specifically, the crop under study is leek, which is the main vegetable crop grown in the area and which is characterized by a high N-demand, making it a particularly interesting case to study. To analyze the fertilizer trade-off with a focus on crop residue-based fertilizers, a selection of a nitrogen-rich mineral fertilizer and four bio-based fertilizers were studied in addition to the option of leaving crop residues on the field. These fertilizers were chosen in accordance with the fertilizers that are currently widely used in Flemish horticulture, however, also allowing for other options in terms of crop residue conversion. A first bio-based fertilizer includes certified compost which can be purchased from waste treatment companies. The second bio-based fertilizer considered in the optimization is pig slurry. Pig cultivation is concentrated in West-Flanders, where leek production is concentrated as well. Given the surplus of animal manure in Flanders, pig slurry is often given away for free. Finally, two bio-based fertilizers are considered that involve conversion of on-farm crop residues. Firstly, following the stewardship business model by De Keyser & Mathijs (2023), we assume that the

farmer can follow the rules of “farm composting” to cooperate with neighboring farmers in converting their crop residues into a compost that resembles the leek compost as described by Viaene (2016). Secondly, we assume that compost from crop residue digestate follows a functionality business model in which the crop residues are collected by a waste treatment company in return for the resulting compost at a fee that corresponds to their average cost multiplied by a profit margin of 20%. Additionally, we assume that the digestate is composted after anaerobic digestion and that the resulting compost has the same composition as certified fruit and vegetable compost. By allowing for different technologies, and thus different fertilizers to be included in our analysis, this provides information about the trade-off between mineral and bio-based fertilizers from both a farmer perspective and a societal perspective.

To determine the socially optimal fertilizer mix, the paper uses a weighted multi-objective optimization approach based on the valuation of environmental externalities to be included in the social cost minimization. Using a cost minimization approach based on LCA, agronomic nitrogen flow simulations and available information on nitrogen, phosphorous and carbon dynamics, this paper aims to give an overview of fertilizer social costs within the Flemish horticultural context. These cost estimations allow for the calculation of the societal optimum that takes fertilizer externalities into account. When these external costs are not internalized, i.e., not incorporated in the decision-making of producers, they are borne by society and an optimal resource allocation will not be realized. If these externalities are internalized (e.g., through policy instruments such as taxes), the farmer will minimize total social costs of fertilization while safeguarding nutrient uptake by crops and keeping in mind the limited availability of resources.

2. Methodology

Optimization research in the fertilizer domain covers a wide range of issues, including cost optimization of fertilizer management, distribution and scheduling (Rodias et al., 2019; Willeghems et al., 2016). Cost minimization models are often solved using linear programming (LP) techniques in which the objective function is optimized subject to a set of linear constraints. This technique involves finding the best possible solution, in which the cost is minimized, from a feasible region defined by the constraints. In comparison to single-objective models, in which either the total costs is minimized or total profit is maximized, multi-objective linear programming (MOLP) models aim to simultaneously optimize multiple objectives, such as economic profitability and environmental sustainability. Some MOLP models have been

introduced to study fertilization decision and crop planning problems from both economic and environmental perspectives. For instance, Prišenk & Turk (2015) developed a MOLP to optimize crop planning on organic farms in Slovenia, while Jain et al. (2021) studied crop pattern optimization in India and Xu et al. (2022) studied the optimization of synergic irrigation and fertilizers in China. Similarly, MOLP models have been used to analyze the optimal use of bio-based resources in different contexts, including the design of bio-based networks for electricity generation in Ghana (Pérez-Fortes et al., 2012), treatment of food waste in China (Deng et al., 2022) and the management of supply chains based on anaerobic digestion in Turkey (Yılmaz Balaman & Selim, 2014). To assess the environmental impacts of fertilizer production and application as part of our optimization model, LCAs were carried out. LCA is a tool which evaluates the effects on the environment by both the use of resources (raw materials, water, energy and other auxiliaries) and the emissions (air, water and soil) due to a given process or product throughout the various stages of its life cycle (raw material extraction and sourcing, manufacturing and processing, transportation, usage, end-of-life). It is an internationally established methodology in the ISO 14040 (2006) series standards. The proposed framework outlines the following four fundamental and iterative phases: (1) Goal and scope definition, (2) Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) analysis, (3) Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA); and, (4) Interpretation (optional).

The goal of this LCA study is to evaluate and compare the environmental effects associated with the production and use of various fertilizer options by an individual farmer. Six scenarios were analyzed, representing five possible alternatives for nitrogen fertilization of leek crops in Flanders: (i) sourcing and use of conventional synthetic fertilizers (urea); (ii) use of locally-sourced pig manure (iii) nutrient supply from certified organic compost; (iv) on-farm compost production from leek residues; (v) converting fruit and vegetable residues including leek residues into digestate and biogas through anaerobic digestion technology, and composting this digestate. Another scenario analyzed in this paper, although not necessarily considered as a potential fertilization strategy, is (vi) the possibility of leaving crop residues on the field by the leek farmer to improve nutrient cycling and, ultimately, soil quality.

This LCA shares the same system boundaries for each scenario, i.e., from the extraction of raw material to field application, and is based on the same functional unit. The functional unit is defined as the common quantified function that all scenarios must provide in order to make them comparable. For the scenarios described in this study, the functional unit is the application of 1 ton of fertilizer. This functional unit was chosen irrespective of the agronomic value, since

a comparison based on agronomic value is carried out in the optimization model. The quantities of fertilizer (application rates) required to provide the functional unit is referred to as reference flow. While the current standard in fertilizer LCA's is to choose a functional unit in terms of provision of nutrients (e.g., kg N), the main goal of our study is not to carry out an LCA but to optimize social costs based on LCA results. For this analysis, a functional unit of 1 ton of fertilizer was more suitable, so that additional constraints including but not limited to the provision of nutrients could be taken into account in the cost minimization model. Figure 1 gives an overview of the methodology used in this study. An expanded cost minimization model is set up for a representative Flemish leek farmer, taking environmental impacts of production, storage and application of fertilizers into account and weighting them by their environmental cost. An important simplifying assumption is that private costs only refer to fertilization costs, so all other costs are considered fixed. To account for uncertainty in the data, several sensitivity analyses are carried out. A first sensitivity analysis investigates the allowable in- or decreases of the models' outcomes, i.e. the amount by which the price or average cost can in- or decrease without changing the optimal application rates. A second way of investigating sensitivity is to run the model with different external cost estimations, distinguishing a lower limit, average and upper limit estimation and thereby inducing different social costs levels. Finally, a last sensitivity analysis method compares the model outcomes with changes in individual data points related to the LCA analysis.

Figure 1: Methodological overview

2.1 The Model

The goal of the cost minimization model is to incorporate environmental impacts into a private cost-minimization model. To include an environmental or social sustainability perspective, researchers have developed multi-objective models in which each dimension of sustainability represents a separate objective (Sazvar et al., 2018). In a first common MOLP-approach, the ϵ -constraint method, the objective functions are converted into constraints. In a second approach, a weighting factor in the form of a vector $w=(w_1, w_2, w_3)$ is added to the objective function such that $\sum_{i=1}^3 w_i = 1$ and $0 \leq w \leq 1$. Then, a linear single-objective programming model is solved for a non-dominated solution (Soltanifar, 2021). Here, an approach is used in which environmental objectives are weighted following their social cost. We specify c_s as social average cost to differentiate between the private and social objective function:

$$(1) \quad \text{Min } C = \sum_f (c_f + c_{s,f}) m_f + \sum_b (c_b + c_{s,b}) m_b$$

where the minimized variable C represents the cost of total fertilizer application per hectare; m_f and m_b are the application rates (ton/ha) of commercial fertilizer f and bio-based fertilizer b per hectare; c_f and $c_{s,f}$ are respectively the price and external costs (€/ton) of fertilizer f ; c_b and $c_{s,b}$ are respectively the average cost and external cost of presumed bio-based fertilizer b . With presumed fertilizer, we mean fertilizer obtained from on-farm crop residues, simultaneously

produced and consumed by the farmer. As such, our commercial fertilizer f also includes bio-based fertilizers produced by other actors, including certified compost and animal manures such as pig slurry.

Following De Keyser et al. (2023), the objective function is subject to the following constraints:

- (2) nitrogen requirement and standard: $N_{min} \leq \sum_f \rho_f N_f m_f + \sum_b \rho_b N_b m_b \leq N_{max}$
- (3) phosphorous standard: $\sum_f P_f m_f + \sum_b P_b m_b \leq P_{max}$
- (4) effective organic carbon: $\sum_f EOC_f m_f + \sum_b EOC_b m_b \geq EOC_{min}$
- (5) residue availability: $\frac{m_b}{r_b} = T$

Constraint 2 and 3 point to the nitrogen and phosphorus matter of the fertilizers: N_f , N_b are respectively the nitrogen content (kg/ton) of purchased fertilizer f and presumed bio-based fertilizer b , while P_f and P_b are their respective phosphorus content (kg/ton). The minimum and maximum values N_{min} , N_{max} and P_{max} define the nutrient concentration range that is required and allowed per hectare following agronomic research and governmental nutrient standards. The nutrient availability coefficient ρ accounts for differences in plant availability of nutrients, equaling 1 for mineral fertilizers. Constraint 4 concerns the Effective Organic Carbon (EOC) content, i.e., the amount of carbon present one year after input to the soil. EOC_{min} is the EOC that is needed to compensate the yearly degradation of organic carbon following best practices (VITO, 2015). The EOC content EOC_f and EOC_b are based on the organic matter content of each fertilizer. It's important to apply a nitrogen-rich fertilizer strategy for leek (Goovaerts & Van Nevel, 2022). With an ample supply in the soil, phosphorus (P) is not limiting for leek growth in Flanders, hence they are not considered in terms of minimal values. Finally, constraint 5 points to the availability of residues: r_b is the volume conversion rate of organic residues to presumed fertilizer b while T is the yearly amount of residues that a prosumer can collect and convert per hectare.

2.2 Data

2.2.1 Fertilizer cost data

For the private cost analysis, fertilizer prices or production cost data were needed in addition to fertilizer requirements and nutrient standards. Fertilizer cost data were retrieved from secondary sources, including data on composting or anaerobic digestion (Agneessens et al., 2014; De Dobbelaere et al., 2015; Pergola et al., 2018), transport (van der Meulen et al., 2020), mineral fertilizer spot prices (IndexMundi, 2023) and energy prices (VREG, 2023). For all

prices and cost data, an average of 2018-2023 price levels was considered. Fertilizer requirements of minimum 80 kg/ha plant available nitrogen and 850 kg/ha EOC were based on D'Haene & Hofman (2019) and VITO (2015). Nutrient standards of maximum 180 kg/ha plant available N, maximum 170 kg/ha total N from animal-based fertilizers and maximum 55 kg/ha P₂O₅ were retrieved from VLM (2023). To attach a weighting factor to each environmental impact associated with fertilizer use, monetary values of externalities were used. We use the values as calculated based on damage costs by de Bruyn et al. (2023). To calculate this, the authors have combined environmental sciences and economic models to arrive to a consistent estimate of external costs associated with emissions.. First, based on literature and policy practice, they established monetary values for effects on human health, ecosystems, buildings and materials, resources and wellbeing. Then, they used economic models to estimate the relationship between these effects and the emissions of primary substances, which leads to an estimation of damage cost per substance.

2.2.2 LCA

2.2.2.1 Production and storage

Inventory data for this LCA were taken from various sources and, whenever possible, adjusted to the local conditions of Flanders. Production data for urea and certified compost are available in the Ecoinvent database (v3.9.1), which is a background LCI database used worldwide for LCA and other environmental assessments. Corbala-Robles et al. (2018) provide inventory data for different pig farming management systems in Flanders. When manure is produced as an output from livestock systems, it is either considered as waste - in which case all system emissions are assigned to the livestock as the main product - or is recognized as a valuable (by-) product contributing to the total emissions from the system. In the case of multi-product inventory, the environmental emissions are allocated between the various co-products by following the stepwise procedure outlined in ISO14044 (ISO 14040, 2006). System expansion or allocation at the point of substitution (APOS) was used for handling multi-output processes in this LCA; also considering the recommendations from the LCA practitioners (see Kytä et al., 2022) on using specific allocation procedure for animal manure. Thus, if the livestock is the main product of interest, one could use system expansion to calculate credits for manure from avoided fertilizer production. On the other hand, if manure is the main product of interest, it should be considered burden-free up to the point where the pig farming process ends, to avoid making arbitrary choices of substituting production of pig meat. However, any emissions deriving from the manure fermentation and storage should be included. Inventory data for on-

site composting can be found in Pergola et al. (2018) and Vandecasteele et al. (2016), while production data for anaerobic digesters were sourced from EcoWerf (2020) and Ecoinvent. The corresponding amount of electricity and natural gas burned for an industrial and district heating (data taken from the Ecoinvent for BE) as avoided products were subtracted from the total impact of digestate production.

LCIA was modelled and computed via the SimaPro 9 software tool from PRé Sustainability (the Netherlands) according to the collected inventory data. 'ReCiPe 2016' hierarchist mid-point impact assessment method version 1.06 was utilized in conducting the impact assessment phase.

2.2.2.2 Application

In this study, environmental impacts of fertilizer application encompass transport emissions, carbon storage, phosphorous leaching, greenhouse gas emissions related to fertilizer application and nitrogen emissions including volatilization, denitrification and leaching.

While environmental impacts associated with transportation of fertilizers from their production site to their point of sale are included in the Ecoinvent database for urea, the emissions were modeled following a freight lorry of 3.5 to 7.5 metric ton for 20 km for certified compost, pig slurry and digestate. For on-farm compost and leaving crop residues on the field, these emissions are not included since the site of production and the site of end-use are the same. For P leaching, the loss coefficients estimated by Corbala-Robles et al. (2018) were used.

In terms of CO₂ and CH₄ emissions, the estimation by Hoxha & Christensen (2019) was used for urea application. For certified compost, reporting by VLACO (2009) was used. The estimations by Walling & Vaneckhaute (2020) were used for pig slurry, on-farm compost and digestate. For crop residues, we calculated an emission factor of 23% based on Janz et al. (2022)¹ and Viaene (2016).

With respect to nitrogen, emissions are modeled with the NDICEA model (van der Burgt & Timmermans, 2010). Table 2 shows the fertilizer composition used to model soil nitrogen dynamics.

¹ Janz et al. (2022) find an emission of 1500 kg CO₂/ha, which is equal to an emission of 409 kg C/ha. With 4 ton/ha DM and a carbon content of 44.7% of DM, crop residues contain 1788 kg C/ha. As such, 23% of the total carbon content is emitted as CO₂.

Table 2: Fertilizer composition used in this study

	Certified fruit and vegetable compost & composted digestate	On-farm composted leek residues	Crop residues	Pig slurry
N (kg/ton)	12	3.2	2.6*	6.40
ρN (kg/ton)	1.8	0.5	0.4*	3.8
P ₂ O ₅ (kg/ton)	6	1.4	0.8*	3.5
DM ^a (kg/ton)	700	401	132	90
OM ^b (kg/ton)	250	143	72	60
Source	Vanrespaille et al. (2018); VLACO (2021)	Viaene et al. (2017)	Viaene (2016)	Vanrespaille et al. (2018); NDICEA

^aDry matter expressed as kg per ton fresh matter

^bOrganic matter expressed as kg per ton fresh matter

^cNutrient availability coefficient ρ accounts for differences in plant availability of N

*Since crop residues are only available in restricted periods throughout the year, it is assumed that the farmer leaves crop residues on the field after harvest as a waste management strategy rather than a fertilizer strategy. Therefore, the nutrient values for crop residues are not considered in the cost optimization model. Nevertheless, the nutrient content of crop residues is indirectly represented in the residual soil N-content taken into account for the formulation of the minimum N-value based on D'Haene and Hofman (2019). Hence, only the organic matter is taken into consideration.

We define the nitrogen footprint based on an emission factor EF. For nitrogen, this emission factor is calculated as follows:

$$(1) \quad EF(\%) = \frac{E_t - E_b}{N} * 100\%$$

Here, E_t is the total emission of N (kg N/ha) from fertilized treatments, E_b is the background emission from the control without N fertilizer application and N refers to the applied fertilizer rate (kg/ha). The total emission and background emission are estimated with NDICEA. The NDICEA model describes soil water and N dynamics. It allows calculation of the N losses due to leaching and denitrification. As leek production in Flanders is concentrated in the West of Flanders, the NDICEA simulation was carried out for a loamy sand soil in the western part of Flanders.

NDICEA estimates the amounts of volatilized, denitrified and leached nitrogen, taking the nutrient content of fertilizers as well as atmospheric deposition of N into account. Without applying any fertilizer (i.e., the background emission) and with leek cultivation after two years of grass clover, the model assumes volatilization of 0 kg/ha, denitrification of 18 kg/ha and N leaching of 34 kg/ha for winter leek. When a fertilizer is applied, these numbers rise. To calculate the emission factors for urea, certified compost and pig slurry, we assume the

application rates needed to provide 80 kg of plant available N, corresponding to the minimum nitrogen requirement as found by D'Haene & Hofman (2019). For presumed fertilizers (i.e., crop residues, on-farm compost and digestate), the application rates are limited by the availability of residues. Considering leek residues, de Ruijter et al. (2010) find that between 20% and 60% of the N content may be leached. The exact amount depends on different factors, including weather conditions. We assume that 16% of the N-content is lost to the air of which 8% is volatilized (de Ruijter et al., 2010) and 8% denitrified.

In addition to the impacts related to N and P application, environmental benefits of carbon sequestration have to be taken into account. While effective organic carbon (EOC) refers to the part of organic C that remains in the soil after one year, C sequestration refers to long-term storage of C in the soil, often referring to 20-100 years. We assume that carbon sequestration rates of residues and slurry are respectively 3.7% and 3.8% of the added carbon (Triberti et al., 2008). For compost, we assume a rate of 8% since carbon sequestration rates are estimated between 2 and 14% (Boldrin et al., 2009).

To attach a weighting factor to each environmental impact associated with fertilizer use, monetary values of externalities were used. The environmental impacts can be converted into monetary terms using environmental shadow prices indicating the welfare loss as a result of the damage caused by the emission. This can be either damage to human health, damage to ecosystems or damage to resource availability. We use the values as calculated based on damage costs by de Bruyn et al. (2023).

Figure 2: From LCA to social costs

3. Results

Following the process depicted in Figure 2, the midpoint LCA results per ton of fertilizer are multiplied with the midpoint damage costs by de Bruyn et al. (2023). The results of this step using the average values by de Bruyn et al. (2023) are represented in Table 3. The intermediary results from the LCA analysis, as well as the lower limit, average and upper limit external cost values as estimated by de Bruyn et al. (2023), are represented in the Appendix.

Table 3: External costs per midpoint category based on the LCA results and the average monetary damage costs by De Bruyn et al. (2023) in €₂₀₂₀/ton

	Urea	Fruit and vegetable compost (certified)	Pig manure	Crop residues	On-farm leek compost	Compost from digestate
Global warming	432.6	28.4	5.7	2.0	2.4	12.9
Stratospheric ozone depletion	8.5	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
Ionizing radiation	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.7
Ozone formation. human health	4.2	1.9	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.7
Ozone formation. terrestrial ecosystems	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Fine particulate matter formation	5218.8	888.4	124.0	34.9	3.8	39.7
Terrestrial acidification	161.9	70.6	3.5	1.0	0.3	2.9
Freshwater eutrophication	1.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Marine eutrophication	44.8	0.3	0.5	1.0	0.2	0.2
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	6.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Freshwater ecotoxicity	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Marine ecotoxicity	1298.3	10.5	0.4	0.0	1.9	-2.1
Human carcinogenic toxicity	27909.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	21906.7	15.4	0.6	0.0	2.7	-3.2
Land use	3.3	2.4	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.7
Mineral resource scarcity	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Fossil resource scarcity	19.6	1.2	0.1	0.0	0.2	-0.1
Water consumption	11.6	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
Total (average)	57030	1020.54	134.98	39.03	11.71	49.64
Total (lower limit)	38124	604.50	79.79	22.91	6.78	26.38
Total (upper limit)	85042	1447.11	189.60	55.12	17.16	67.82

Compared to the other impact categories, the external costs are relatively high for fine particulate matter formation for all fertilizers under study. This is related to the high damage cost for fine particulate matter, which can be traced back to the damage costs to human health, including aggravation of pulmonary and heart diseases (de Bruyn et al., 2023). Combustion is an important source of fine particulate matter, as are secondary aerosols from emission of SO₂, NH₃ and NO_x (de Bruyn et al., 2023). Other high external costs per ton of fertilizer, especially for urea, are related to global warming, terrestrial acidification, marine ecotoxicity and human toxicity. However, these environmental impacts and the environmental costs related to these impacts, are not yet comparable in terms of agronomic value, resource availability, nutrient standards and farmers' costs. The LCA results serve as intermediary outcomes that inform the cost minimization models, where these impacts are integrated into the overall assessment. Without the inclusion of external costs to reflect environmental impacts, a farmer's rationale could be represented with a private cost minimization model of which the results are presented in Table 4. In this case, it is optimal for the leek farmer to use pig slurry in addition to compost and mineral fertilizers. However, the reduced cost for compost from digestate is relatively low, indicating that it would be profitable to use some compost from crop residue digestate as soon as the cost for this BBF lowers by €0.65/ton. Additionally, the allowable increase, i.e. the amount by which the price or average cost can increase without changing the optimum, of pig slurry is €4.15/ton. As soon as the cost of pig slurry exceeds this, it becomes unprofitable to use raw pig slurry as a fertilizer.

Table 4: Optimization – minimizing private costs, and sensitivity analysis

	Urea	Certified FVG-compost	Pig slurry	Crop residues	Crop residue compost	Compost from crop residue digestate
Optimum (ton/ha)	0.06	4	12	25	0	0
Obj. value (€/ton)	358.69	15.10	0	00	10.21	12.78
Red. cost (€/ton)	0	0	0	0	5.64	0.65
All. incr. (ton/ha)	1E+30	0.8	4.15	0.26	1E+30	1E+30
All. decr. (ton/ha)	358.69	16.26	1E+30	1E+30	5.64	0.65

Optimum = application rate in the optimum; Obj. value = price or average production cost;

Sensitivity analysis: Red. cost = the amount by which the price or average cost would have to improve for the fertilizer to be applied in the optimum; All. incr. = the amount by which the price or average cost can increase without changing the optimum; All. decr. = the amount by which the price or average cost can decrease without changing the optimum

Nevertheless, external costs that are borne by society can be integrated in this cost minimization model by considering social costs rather than private costs (i.e., equation 1). Farmers generally do not consider external or social costs because these are not reflected in their private costs. However, if policy instruments such as taxes are introduced, these social costs will be incorporated into their private costs, prompting farmers to take them into account. The results of the social cost minimization are presented in Table 5. For all estimations of social costs, the optimum includes application of 60 kg/ha urea, 5 tons crop residues and 4 tons compost from digestate.

Sensitivity analysis provides insight in how the optimal solution changes when specific parameters change. A first type of sensitivity analysis is carried out with regard to total costs (i.e. private and social costs). With a lower and upper limit of external cost estimates, the allowable increases and decreases are relatively large (Table 5). In other words, the results are quite robust to changes in externality valuation.

However, a second type of sensitivity analysis can be carried out by investigating the allowable increase and decrease, respectively indicating the amount by which the cost can increase or decrease without changing the optimum. This analysis points out that if the costs of pig slurry become sufficiently high, the results might change: the allowable increase values in Table 5 show that the results would change if the social cost of pig slurry increases by €81/ton, €104/ton, or €156/ton, respectively, in the lower limit, average or upper limit estimations. A similar reasoning holds for crop residues: if their social costs increase by €25/ton, €24/ton or €40/ton respectively in the lower limit, average or upper limit estimations, the results change as well.

To explore this based on the external costs, Table 3 gives an indication of the impacts that are conclusive in the calculation of each fertilizer's external cost. Both for pig slurry and crop residues, the impacts related to fine particulate matter represent more than 90% of their external cost valuation.

Table 5: Optimization – minimizing social costs, and sensitivity analysis

	Urea	Certified FVG- compost	Pig slurry	Crop residues	Crop residue compost	Compost from crop residue digestate
Lower limit – Total cost: €3777/ha						
Optimum (ton/ha)	0.06	0	12	20	0	4
Obj. value (€/ton)	38483	620	80	23	17	39
Red. cost (€/ton)	0	600	0	0	16	0
All. incr. (€/ton)	2133006	1E+30	81	25	1E+30	33
All. decr. (€/ton)	19241	600	8069	497	16	70
Average – Total cost: €5940/ha						
Optimum (ton/ha)	0.06	0	12	20	0	4
Obj. value (€/ton)	57389	1036	135	39	22	62
Red. cost (€/ton)	0	1009	0	0	15	0
All. incr. (€/ton)	3587098	1E+30	104	24	1E+30	32
All. decr. (€/ton)	18535	1009	13569	835	15	89
Upper limit – Total cost: €8584/ha						
Optimum (ton/ha)	0.06	0	12	20	0	4
Obj. value (€/ton)	85401	1462	190	55	27	81
Red. cost (€/ton)	0	1431	0	0	25	0
All. incr. (€/ton)	5089592	1E+30	156	40	1E+30	53
All. decr. (€/ton)	30508	1431	19252	1185	25	134

Optimum = application rate in the optimum; Obj. value = price or average production cost;

Sensitivity analysis: Red. cost = the amount by which the price or average cost would have to improve for the fertilizer to be applied in the optimum; All. incr. = the amount by which the price or average cost can increase without changing the optimum; All. decr. = the amount by which the price or average cost can decrease without changing the optimum

The LCA results point out that this impact is related to the ammonia emissions. As such, the main cause of uncertainty is related to the ammonia emissions. This allows testing of two final sensitivity scenarios: (1) increased ammonia emissions for pig slurry and (2) increased ammonia emissions for crop residues. Considering the former, Table 5 shows that the results would change from a social cost of €161/ton onwards, equaling the sum of the objective value (80) and the allowable increase of pig slurry (81) in the lower limit estimation. This would be the case when the fine particulate matter impacts, and consequently the ammonia emissions, increase by a factor of 2.1. With a similar reasoning, the results would change if the ammonia emissions for crop residues increase by a factor of 2.3. Using the lower limit environmental cost estimates, the results of these two scenarios are represented in Table 6. We conducted sensitivity analyses on all other emissions, but the results remained unchanged.

Table 6: Optimization – minimizing social costs in two sensitivity scenarios

	Urea	Certified FVG- compost	Pig slurry	Crop residues	Crop residue compost	Compost from crop residue digestate
(1) Pig slurry - ammonia emissions *2.1						
Optimum (ton/ha)	0.10	0	0	5	0	18
Obj. value (€/ton)	38483	620	170	23	17	39
Red. cost (€/ton)	0	606	9	0	16	0
All. incr. (€/ton)	2301	1E+30	1E+30	25	1E+30	7
All. decr. (€/ton)	19244	606	9	7	16	1E+30
(2) Crop residues - ammonia emissions *2.3						
Optimum (ton/ha)	0.06	0	12	15	9	0
Obj. value (€/ton)	38483	620	80	51	17	39
Red. cost (€/ton)	0	637	0	0	0	3
All. incr. (€/ton)	1973	1E+30	41	15	2	1E+30
All. decr. (€/ton)	7151	637	8662	3	17	3

Optimum = application rate in the optimum; Obj. value = price or average production cost;

Sensitivity analysis: Red. cost = the amount by which the price or average cost would have to improve for the fertilizer to be applied in the optimum; All. incr. = the amount by which the price or average cost can increase without changing the optimum; All. decr. = the amount by which the price or average cost can decrease without changing the optimum

It becomes clear that, in a scenario with increased ammonia emission of pig slurry, it is not optimal to use pig slurry. This could for example be the case when inadequate manure storage systems are used, without proper covering or containment. Instead, the optimal fertilizer mix includes a mix of mineral fertilizer and compost from digestate, with the latter applied until the phosphorous limit is reached and the leftover crop residues left on the field. In a scenario with increased ammonia emissions of crop residues, however, it is optimal to convert part of these crop residues into on-farm compost, while still using pig slurry and mineral fertilizers. This is also the case when social cost of compost from AD exceed the allowable increase values in Table 5. However, this increase in social costs cannot be traced back to ammonia emissions alone since transport emissions also contribute significantly to fine particulate matter impacts for compost from AD, and was therefore not included as a sensitivity scenario.

4. Discussion

While some previous optimization studies have incorporated social costs in the circular economy (Mavrotas et al., 2015) and bio-economy (Tiammee & Likasiri, 2020; Ul Haq et al., 2020), few studies focus on the trade-off between mineral and bio-based fertilizers. The present study was designed to determine the optimal application rates of mineral and bio-based fertilizers in leek farming in Flanders considering private and external costs.

Total social costs in the optimum amount to €3773/ha, €5935/ha, and €8584/ha respectively, following the lower limit, average and upper limit social cost values, compared to a private total cost of €81/ha. For reference, with an average marketable yield of 50 ton/ha (D'Haene & Hofman, 2019) and an average price of €0.54/kg and €0.86/kg in 2020 and 2021 (Vilt, 2022), the average revenue for leek would be between €27 000/ha and €43 000/ha.

In comparison to the private cost optimization results, the main difference is that, from a societal perspective, it would be interesting to convert part of the crop residues into compost from digestate instead of buying certified compost and leaving all crop residues on the field. This compost is the biggest source of organic carbon. Indeed, a study by Viaene et al. (2017) indicates the potential of treating leek residues, for instance through composting and/or digesting, as a promising alternative for incorporation of fresh vegetable crop residues. The authors point out that treatment allows to process and store the residues during winter, thereby reducing the risk for N losses due to the fast decomposition of crop residues, while improving soil quality and closing local nutrient cycles. Apart from this finding, the fertilizers used in the socially optimal fertilizer mix are the same as those in the private mix, indicating that both mineral fertilizers such as urea and bio-based fertilizers such as pig slurry and compost play significant roles in achieving the desired nutrient balance. However, with higher ammonia emissions related to pig manure storage and application than the NDICEA output used in this study, for instance as estimated by Corbala-Robles et al. (2018) and Makara et al. (2019), it might be more optimal to convert even more crop residues into compost from digestate and leave out pig slurry application. While this could be related to inadequate manure storage, this could also be useful in regions with a lower availability of pig slurry or in projected situations where a smaller animal industry is anticipated in Flanders, as suggested by several academics to tackle sustainability challenges (Vlaamse Landmaatschappij, 2022). If not, however, this shift may indicate an increase in manure processing and export. In that case, part of the crop residues would be removed and converted into compost which would be applied until the maximum phosphorous standard is met, and all other crop residues would be left on the field. Finally, if ammonia emissions related to on-field crop residue degradation would be higher than our initial estimate, it could be more interesting to convert part of the crop residues into on-farm compost through a stewardship model in which the farmer cooperates with other farmers, while also applying pig slurry. Nevertheless, considering mineral fertilizers, the results show that despite their environmental costs, they have an important role to play in nutrient provision.

The study is subject to some limitations that are mainly related to data availability and representativeness. The environmental costs as valued by de Bruyn et al. (2023) are specific for the Netherlands. Especially for air pollutants that enter the human body by respiration, such as fine particulate matter, the impacts can vary according to local circumstances and type of emissions (de Bruyn et al., 2023). However, given geographical proximity and comparability in terms of environmental issues and practices, it can be assumed that these values are a close approximation for Flanders. The use of secondary data to carry out the LCA in this study also brings along issues of representativeness in terms of geographical, economic or time-related scope. However, we address these uncertainties by using cost ranges and carrying out extensive sensitivity analysis. Moreover, the goal of this study was not to carry out an impact assessment, nor to carry out a monetary valuation study, but to incorporate environmental costs in a cost optimization model to determine an optimal fertilizer mix. Additionally, it is essential to acknowledge a limitation related to the methodology. The LCAs conducted in this research were attributional in nature. A notable drawback is that the assessments do not consider the consequential impacts that might arise from changes in practices. For instance, we do not account for potential alternative uses of fertilizers such as pig slurry. Another limitation is the assumption that manure is burden-free up to the point where the pig farming process ends. This simplification may overlook potential environmental impacts associated with manure production during the pig farming process (Olofsson & Börjesson, 2018). Estimating the impacts of pig slurry with another type of allocation could increase its external costs. If this leads to a social cost increase of €81/ton or more, this would imply the optimal solution of sensitivity scenario (1) which does not involve the application of pig slurry. Nevertheless, the aim of this study is not to evaluate externalities but to demonstrate how this data could be used for decision-making by farmers and policy-makers. This way, the model can also be used to evaluate decision-making for other crops and other regions.

The findings in this study are in line with previous research favoring combined fertilization strategies, where both bio-based and mineral fertilizers are used (Jiang et al., 2018; Shi et al., 2023). The study suggests that mineral fertilizers have an important place in the fertilizer mix for Flemish leek to maintain yields, even when fertilizer externalities are considered (Table 5 and 6), which corroborates findings of Santolin et al., (2024). While there is a role for bio-based fertilizers, mineral fertilizer application will remain important if current minimal nitrogen provision levels are required and fertilizer standards are maintained. Nevertheless, in the social optimum, bio-based fertilizers also play a large role: in both the private and social

optimum, it is relevant to use manure-based fertilizers, given that their ammonia emissions remain within acceptable limits. This can, for instance, be mitigated with adequate storage systems (Corbala-Robles et al., 2018). Additionally, it is important that crop residues are put to good use, for example by producing biogas and using the leftover digestate as a fertilizer. Previous research points out that stable business models are needed to establish bio-based fertilizer technologies in the market (Chojnacka et al., 2019). This study contributes to addressing this need by proving the social benefits of a strategy wherein crop residues are partially converted to compost through collaborative efforts along the value chain.

Recommendations for practice

Based on these findings, some recommendations can be made for farm managers looking to align their practices with those that minimize environmental costs. Currently, many Flemish horticultural farmers cultivating leek use a combination pig slurry and mineral nitrogen, with representative rates of roughly 20 ton/ha pig slurry and 80 kg mineral N/ha (Inagro, 2022). Our analyses point towards possible costs savings, both private and social costs, by using less of both. A balanced approach incorporating both mineral and bio-based fertilizers can ensure a cost-optimal and adequate nutrient provision while minimizing environmental impacts. Additionally, in contrast to the current practice of leaving crop residues on the field, our findings indicate that it can be interesting cooperate with other value chain actors for the treatment of crop residues. However, this balance will differ for different crops and regions. Finally, it is important to monitor ammonia emissions to ensure minimal external costs.

5. Conclusions

This study set out to determine the optimal application rates of mineral and bio-based fertilizers considering social costs as the sum of private and external costs, applied to a conceptualized case of leek cultivation in Flanders. In doing so, the study focused on different options to use crop residues as fertilizer strategies.

The results confirm that there is a case for converting part of the crop residues into compost through anaerobic digestion. This supports the idea that value chain cooperation between waste management companies and farmers could provide societal benefits. A second major finding is that both mineral and bio-based fertilizers, including animal manure, can be socially optimal and complement each other. Finally, the study confirms the relevance of ammonia emissions in terms of social costs, proving that the composition of the socially optimal fertilizer mix depends on their ammonia emissions.

This paper offers some insights into the trade-offs between fertilizers including private and environmental costs. These findings help to understand the formulation of an optimal fertilizer mix from a societal perspective. Additionally, they imply that internalization of externalities does not necessarily result in circularity. These results have implications for farmers and policy makers wishing to internalize fertilizer externalities. For example, crop residue conversion and cooperation between farmers and waste treatment companies, as assumed in our estimation of compost from digestate, can be encouraged.

There are still many unanswered questions related to the internalization of fertilizer externalities with policy measures, including pricing mechanisms, monitoring and enforcement, spatial and temporal variability and distributional impacts. This is an important issue for future research. Additionally, future research can evaluate optimal fertilizer application rates in other regions and for other crops or rotations. Furthermore, additional research is needed to incorporate consequential LCAs, providing a more nuanced understanding of the implications of recommended changes in practices.

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Appendix

Figure 3: LCA results per ton of fertilizer

The bar chart in figure 2 represents the LCA results with a functional unit of 1 ton of fertilizer, as used in the cost minimization model. However, these intermediary results should be interpreted with caution, as they do not represent the agronomic value of the fertilizers as included in the cost minimization model. For the purpose of illustration, figure 3 includes the LCA results per kg of plant available nitrogen (PAN).

Figure 4: LCA results per kg of N

Table A1: LCA results per ReCiPe midpoint category (own analysis) and corresponding external costs

	Unit	Urea	Fruit and vegetable compost (certified)	Pig manure	Crop residues	On-farm leek compost	Compost from digestate	External cost LL* (€ ₂₀₂₀ /unit)	External cost AVG* (€ ₂₀₂₀ /unit)	External cost UL* (€ ₂₀₂₀ /unit)
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq/ton	3327.64	218.57	43.55	15.76	18.35	99.55	0.05	0.13	0.16
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC ₁₁ eq	0.29	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.20	29.10	69.60
Ionizing radiation	kg Co-60eq	75.84	107.06	1.10	0.00	2.79	-164.23	0.00	0.00	0.01
Ozone formation. human health	kg NO _x eq/ton	2.48	1.14	0.03	0.00	0.04	0.39	0.99	1.70	2.21
Ozone formation. terrestrial ecosystems	kg NO _x eq/ton	2.76	1.16	0.03	0.00	0.05	0.41	0.04	0.04	0.15
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM _{2.5} eq/ton	31.06	5.29	0.74	0.21	0.02	0.24	101.20	168.00	235.00
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq/ton	25.06	10.93	0.54	0.15	0.05	0.46	3.38	6.46	10.72
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq/ton	0.22	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.56	5.53	10.13
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq/ton	3.14	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.01	0.01	7.64	14.25	27.60
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1.4DCB/ton	7112.72	24.09	3.59	0.00	5.95	11.67	0.00	0.00	0.00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1.4DCB/ton	65.15	0.43	0.02	0.00	0.08	-0.10	0.02	0.03	0.04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1.4DCB/ton	276241.09	2224.32	84.20	0.00	396.36	-454.60	0.00	0.00	0.01
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1.4DCB/ton	5316.04	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	3.55	5.25	7.91
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1.4DCB/ton	225842.19	158.82	6.06	0.00	28.33	-32.92	0.07	0.10	0.15
Land use	m ³ crop eq/ton	22.40	16.69	0.41	0.00	0.66	-4.82	0.10	0.15	0.19
Mineral resource scarcity	kg CU eq/ton	6.66	0.82	0.03	0.00	0.12	-0.34	0.00	0.01	0.08
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq/ton	699.32	44.64	3.41	0.00	7.45	-3.10	0.00	0.03	0.16

Water consumption	m ³ /ton	84.69	1.35	0.02	0.00	0.05	-0.92	0.00	0.14	0.18
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*External cost monetization values from de Bruyn et al. (2023)

Figure 5: LCA results per ton of fertilizer

The bar chart in figure 2 represents the LCA results with a functional unit of 1 ton of fertilizer, as used in the cost minimization model. However, these intermediary results should be interpreted with caution, as they do not represent the agronomic value of the fertilizers as included in the cost minimization model. For the purpose of illustration, figure 3 includes the LCA results per kg of plant available nitrogen (PAN).

Figure 6: LCA results per kg of N